

Cycling and Correlations in Quantum Mixed States

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In an earlier note, bound pure states were described in terms of cycling of momentum states $\exp(ipx)$ which scattered off a potential $V(x)$ from one momentum state into another in a time of $1/E$. If the average kinetic energy, defined by $[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad f_p \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$, where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \quad f_p \exp(ipx) = \text{normalization constant}$, satisfies a conservation of energy equation: $\text{KE ave} + V(x) = E$, one obtains the time-independent Schrodinger equation. It was also argued the Schrodinger equation may be written in terms of a cycling equation by writing both $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as a Fourier series and equating $\exp(ipx)$ terms, namely:

$$\text{Sum } k+j=p \quad V_k f_j + p^2/2m f_p = E f_p \quad ((1))$$

In other words, f_j scatter with f_k to produce f_p and potential energy, which together with the kinetic energy of f_p yield a constant (energy) times f_p . This is of the form of an equation with a separable time portion $\text{id}/\text{dt } W(t,x) = E W(x)$. It should be noted that in ((1)), the f_j 's are correlated with f_p . In this note, we try to argue that quantum bound states demonstrate strong correlations between f_p 's and also try to extend the cycling model described above to mixed states.

Correlations in Single Particle States

Quantum mechanics is often described in terms of wave mechanics and interference. Here we try to argue a quantum particle, such as an electron, may have an internal cycling or zitterbewegung motion which allows it to be modeled by $\exp[i(-kx + Et)]$. One may consider a particle moving forward $\exp[i(-kx + Et)]$ and one moving backward $\exp[i(kx + Et)]$. These appear to be uncorrelated. If the electron is put into a box with no potential, it bounces back and forth and interference is said to occur. Thus, one adds $\exp[i(kx + Et)]$ and $\exp[i(-kx + Et)]$ to obtain a real function, $\cos(kx)$. We argue that in such a case, the forward and backward motion become correlated to form a resonance state. Each motion has its own internal cycling. At the right wall, the forward moving particle, which is cycling, must transform into a backward moving particle in a smooth manner. We argue this may account for the discrete levels of such a system. These levels represent forward and backward motion becoming correlated to form a state "cos(kx)" with $k=6.28n/L$ with L being the length of the one dimensional box. (Note: there is no phase between the $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-kx)$ and this seems to indicate a kind of correlation.) The forward and backward motion each retain their own cycling, but through interference i.e. correlation form a resonance. (For the case of $\sin(kx)$ wave, a phase shift of 3.14 is present.)

Imagine a potential added to the box which has walls with a potential of infinity. Then, the correlated resonance (of forward and backward motion) $\cos(kx)$ is not broken. In fact, one uses

many $\cos(kn x)$ states which interfere, i.e. become correlated, to form a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_{kn} f(kn) \cos(kn x)$. Thus, one starts with an internal resonance due to cycling in a quantum particle, next forms a resonance of the forward and backward motion through correlation (i.e. interference), then uses these resonances as building blocks of a new resonance. Thus, these are correlated building blocks.

For the case in which there is no infinite potential at the walls of the box, things are a little different, but it seems that general ideas are the same. Consider a system with a potential, but no walls. Let the system have even symmetry. Then, $\cos(kx)$ will still be a building block of the new resonance i.e. wavefunction $W(x)$. Note: $\cos(kx)$ has no phase between $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$ and so we argue the forward and backward wave are correlated through interference. For such a system one has the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$(-1/2m) d^2/dx^2 W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((2))$$

If one writes $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as Fourier series and equates $\exp(ipx)$ terms, one has:

$$(-1/2m) f_p p^2/2m + \sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_j = E f_p \quad ((3))$$

We argue this represents a correlation equation as f_j 's combine with V_k 's to form f_p . This creates potential energy for a particular f_p which combined with kinetic energy yields total energy. We argue it also represents a cycling equation which creates an equilibrium state for each p . The various f_j 's combine with V_k 's in such a way that when added to $p^2/2m f_p$ one obtains a constant E times f_p , i.e. each f_p cycles through time as $\exp(iEt)$. Thus, there seems to be a resonance as all f_p 's have the same cycling based on one E . $1/E$ represents the cycling time. We argue this is a kind of resonance based on correlations between the f_p 's. A question now arises as to how to treat mixed states.

Mixed States

As an example of a mixed state, consider the ground state of the deuteron. In general, one has a Hamiltonian H_0 which commutes with L^2 (angular momentum) and an unknown small perturbative potential. Thus, one can solve the time-independent Schrodinger equation for H_0 obtaining bound pure states of $W_0(x)$ with E_0 , $W_1(x)$ with E_1 etc. This also have a distinct magnitude of angular momentum $L(L+1)$. If the perturbation were not present, then the ground state would be $W_0(x)$.

Consider for a moment a perturbation in the form of a photon with energy $E_1 - E_0$ and only the Hamiltonian H_0 . In such a case, one moves from a resonance E_0 and W_0 i.e. the ground state to the new resonance E_1 and W_1 . There is no longer a W_0 , so the correlated plane wave states in W_0 are transformed into a new set of correlated plane wave states in W_1 . Both W_0 and W_1 represent correlated plane wave states, but there is no correlation between W_0 and W_1 . One has one or the other and a photon can be absorbed or emitted.

Such does not seem to be the case with the small perturbation added to H_0 to form the deuteron Hamiltonian. If the perturbation is small, one may guess that $W(x) = bW_0(x) + g(x)$, where $g(x)$ is a small correction. Noting that the solutions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation for H_0 yield a complete orthonormal set $W_i(x)$ $i=0,1,2$ etc one may write $g(x)$ as a linear combination of these. One may, however, use any complete, orthonormal set of functions to do the same thing. One may also apply the same argument to $W(x)$. In the case of $W(x)$, however, the first leading term should be related to $W_0(x)$, as H_0 is the dominant part of the Hamiltonian. In such a case, other W_i 's with $i>0$ may make up $g(x)$. In order to have the lowest energy, one might argue one wants only $W_1(x)$ as other eigenstates will bring in energies such as E_2, E_3 etc. At this point, only math arguments have been made.

In this note, we try to argue there is something physically essential about resonance states such as $W_0(x)$ and $W_1(x)$. If the perturbation were not present, $W_0(x)$ would represent the stable ground state and $W_1(x)$ a metastable first excited state. Thus, these states are physical as other imagined states are unstable. These states as argued above represent correlated fp's forming a cycling resonance governed by $\exp(iEt)$. Thus, it seems if one has a ground state resonance and perturbs it, it may try to form other resonance states instead of arbitrary states in order to be metastable (It may actually try to form arbitrary states, but these would be unstable and decay right away.) Unlike the case of the photon, one cannot transform entirely into the state W_1 or emit a photon and drop back to W_0 . Nevertheless W_0 and W_1 are fp correlated resonance states which become correlated between themselves (i.e. interfere) to produce a new overall resonance state. This is similar to the $\cos(kx)$ resonances becoming correlated to produce $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \text{ fp } \cos(px)$.

Consider ((3)). This can be applied to both W_0 and W_1 , namely:

$$p^*p/2m f_{0p} + \sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_{0j} = E_0 f_{0p} \quad \text{and} \quad p^*p/2m f_{1p} + \sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_{1j} = E_1 f_{1p} \quad ((4))$$

If one forms the linear combination $b f_{0p} + a f_{1p}$ one has:

$$p^*p/2m (b f_{0p} + a f_{1p}) + \sum_{j+k=p} V_k (b f_{0j} + a f_{1j}) = E_0 b f_{0p} + E_1 a f_{1p} \quad ((5))$$

Thus, one has two resonances in fp's, but these are becoming correlated. If one converts back to space coordinates, the right hand side of ((5)) is $E_0 b W_0(x) + E_1 a W_1(x)$. If one multiplies by $b W_0(x) + a W_1(x)$ with $(a^*a + b^*b = 1)$ for normalization) and integrates one finds an average energy of: $E_0 b^*b + E_1 a^*a$. ((6))

Now one may ask whether the linear combination used in ((5)) actually leads to a new resonance state, namely whether there is a connection with:

$$(H_0 + V_{\text{pert}}) W(x) = E W(x) \quad \text{where } V_{\text{pert}} = V \text{ perturbation} \quad ((7))$$

If the two are related, one would expect $E = E_0 b^*b + E_1 a^*a$. This E would be the new cycling frequency and the cycling frequencies of E_0 and E_1 would be combined, in a sense disappearing from the problem just as $\exp(-p^*p/2m t)$ disappears from ((3)) and only the overall E remains.

If this is the case, one would expect that $W(x) = b W_0(x) + a W_1(x)$ i.e.

$bE_0 W_0 + a E_1 W_1 = E W$. Multiplying the left-hand side by $b W_0 + a W_1$ and the right by W and integrating yields $b^*b E_0 + a^*a E_1 = E$ as desired.

Next, consider $\langle W | V_{\text{pert}} | W \rangle$ with

$$V_{\text{pert}} W(x) = (E - H_0) W = E W - H_0 (b W_0 + a W_1) = E W - E_0 b W_0 - a E_1 W_1$$

Multiplying by $W = b W_0 + a W_1$ and integrating gives:

$$\langle W | V_{\text{pert}} | W \rangle = E - (E_0 b^*b + a^*a E_1) = 0. \quad ((8))$$

Thus, it seems the mixed state $b W_0(x) + a W_1(x)$ is equivalent to a new resonance state $W(x)$ with a resonance frequency of $E = E_0 b^*b + a^*a E_1$. Thus, resonances such as W_0 and W_1 can become correlated (interfere) to form a new overall resonance. It is the overall energy which dictates the cycling frequency of the new overall resonance. The mixed state (of wavefunctions of one Hamiltonian H_0) is equivalent to a pure state of a new Hamiltonian $H_0 + V_{\text{pert}}$.

Visualizing the New Resonance in Terms of the Old Resonances

One may ask how one may visualize the old resonances W_0 and W_1 in the new resonance W . First of all, the probability for momentum is correlated i.e. there is interference i.e.

$$P(p) = f_{\text{new}}(p) * f_{\text{new}}(p) = b^*b f_{p_0} * f_{p_0} + a^*a f_{p_1} * f_{p_1} + 2 ab f_{p_0} * f_{p_1} \quad ((9))$$

Next consider the idea of a quasiparticle. For a pure state in ((3)), the quasiparticle is described by:

$$W(x) = \int f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((10))$$

If one sums over p one has $W(x)W(x)$, the density. Thus, a quasiparticle plane wave with weight f_p moves through space as $\exp(ipx)$, but picks up an amplitude $W(x) = \sum_k f_k \exp(ikx)$. This shows how the quasiparticle f_p is correlated with the other f_k 's.

For the mixed state, one has:

$$(b W_0 + a W_1) (b f_{p_0} + a f_{p_1}) \exp(ipx) = b^*b W_0 f_{p_0} \exp(ipx) + a^*a W_1 f_{p_1} \exp(ipx) +$$

$$b a W_0 f_1 p \exp(ipx) + b a W_1 f_0 p \exp(ipx) \quad ((11))$$

Thus, the quasiparticle of the new resonance is complicated. It has two terms representing quasiparticles of the W_0 and W_1 resonances and two interference terms. The W_0 and W_1 resonance terms show that $f_0 p$ is correlated with the $f_0 k$'s in W_0 and $f_1 p$ with the $f_1 k$'s in W_1 . The two interference terms show that $f_1 p$ is correlated with the $f_0 k$'s in $W_0(x)$ and $f_0 p$ with the $f_1 k$'s in W_1 . Thus, there is a complicated set of correlations which describe how the two resonances interact (interfere) to form the new resonance with energy $b^*b E_0 + a^*a E_1$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue that quantum bound states involve correlations between momentum plane wave states. For a single particle in a box, these correlations lead to $\cos(kx)$ i.e. the forward and backward wave have the same phase and a resonance is formed. For bound states, we argue there is a cycling correlation relating each f_p to f_k 's where the wavefunction $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p f_p \exp(ipx)$. In the case of a mixed state, such as a deuteron, one has $H = H_0 + V_{\text{perturbation}}$, where V_{pert} is small. One would expect a leading term similar to W_0 namely $b W_0$. We argue that physically the system seeks other resonance terms of H_0 because these are metastable. The simplest solution is $b W_0 + a W_1$ with $b^*b + a^*a = 1$ for normalization. These are two resonances W_0 and W_1 which now become correlated (interfere). We try to show this leads to a new overall resonance with energy $b^*b E_0 + a^*a E_1$. It is this new energy which describes the overall cycling of the new overall resonance. Thus, it seems that quantum mechanics may be a statistical theory, but one with many correlations existing at the wavefunction level. The wavefunction, in turn, is related to conditional probabilities such as $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$. The wavefunction is a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation which demonstrates correlation clearly (for example between f_p 's). When one moves to the level of straight probabilities, such as $P(p) = f_p^* f_p$ or $P(x) = W(x) W(x)^*$, outwardly it appears that one has regular statistical equations. For example, $KE = \text{Sum on } p p^* p / 2m P(p)$ or $\text{Average of } V(x) = \text{Integral over } x V(x) P(x)$. The values of $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, however, exhibit the consequences of internal correlations. For example, $P(x)$ shows results of interference already for a particle moving forward and backward in a box.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2019)